

THE ROLE OF PRODUCT TRUST AND GREEN PRODUCT KNOWLEDGE ON GREEN PRODUCT PURCHASE INTENTION

JAI KUMAR K R

Research Scholar, Mail Id:Jai.Pitam@Gmail.Com

Dr. G. BRINDHA

H.O.D, Faculty of Management Studies, Dr. M.G.R. Educational and Research Institue.

Abstract

In a developing country like India, conservation of land, water and animals has become a major issue. The green environment is an important environmental concern of the consumers which has resulted in the emergence of various green products. The aim of the study is to know the factors influencing green product purchase intention. Simple random sampling method was used to collect the data among green product users. A well-developed questionnaire was used to collect the data. SPSS was used to analyse the data. It was found that factors such as green product trust and green product knowledge is found to be the most influencing factor for the green product purchase intention. The study implies that people should be given knowledge regard to the performance of the green product and developing trust in the minds of the consumers to be focused by the manufacturers and seller of green products

Keywords: Green product intention, green product knowledge, product trust, green product positioning, attitude towards green product

INTRODUCTION

In recent times, sustainable development has become a major issue in the world. Sustainability is the main focus of Sustainable goals. Sustainable Goal no: 12, Responsible production and consumption were directly linked to a green environment. The green environment is an important environmental concern of the consumers which has resulted in the emergence of various green products. This environmental concern from the consumers has created an increase in demand for environmentally friendly products. Consumers gradually shifted their purchase pattern towards eco-friendly products. There exist a positive behaviour towards green products (**Chen and Chang, 2012 and suki, 2016.**) Green product consumerism has emerged as a trending area of research (**Lai & Cheng, 2016**). People and governments are more about the deterioration of the environment and ecological challenges. Protecting natural resources has been the prime concern of consumers, business houses, and the government during the last three decades. This resulted in green production, green brands among production houses and green consumption, green product awareness among consumers of late.

As environmental awareness has increased among consumers, companies are aware of the need of the consumers as a result they try to follow specific activities in many forms of their business to attain sustainable goals.

In a developing country like India, conservation of land, water and animals has become a major issue. Also, population growth is a major factor in developing countries where the urban

population is at a higher percentage due to employment. The urban population in Asia has reached close to 55%. As the population grows, the demand is high for certain commodities which is the driving force for mass production. For this mass production to meet the demands of the consumers production houses overlooked the environmental deterioration due to their business activities.

But after the Rio conference conducted by the United Nations conference on environment and development, 1992, the business houses turned their business process to get along with green product demand by the consumers. The United Nations sustainable development goal 2030 has pressed all the nations to attain sustainable development goals in 2030.

As a result, new production process and consumption pattern has developed and people's food consumption has figured in such a way that organic food procured and consumer goods to be eco-friendly from raw material procurement till the end of the product usage. Green awareness, increased health awareness, growth in educated social groups, increased consumer disposable earnings, and higher food costs have all contributed to the significant growth in the organic market. Therefore, a study about green product purchase intention is the need of the hour.

Research questions

1. What are the factors which influence the consumer buying intention towards green products?

Research objectives

1. To estimate Green Product Positioning (GPP), Green Brand Knowledge (GPK), Green Brand Attitude (GPA), and customers Purchase Intention.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Green Trust:

Green Trust is defined as a belief that is derived from the credibility, compassion, and the concern that the product has on its own impact created on the environment which resulted in the readiness to rely on a product, service, or a brand. (Chen, Y. S., & Chang, C. H. 2013)

According to (Krystallis & Chrysohoidis, 2005) trust in the certification of organic products is one of the factors among food quality, Security, and brand name that affect the consumers' willingness to pay for organic foods was found in research conducted among Greek population.

Green consumption of UK residents is mainly related to their trust of sources like government, Environmental NGOs, European environmental authorities, and private business houses as the research result obtained by (Darnall, Ponting, & Vazquez-Brust, 2012).

The authenticity of the products claimed to be organic plays a vital role in the decision making towards the purchase of organic products. A low level of trust towards the credibility of the organic products labelling is found among the people of Taiwanese under the study which heavily influence the purchase decision of the green products. (Tung et al., 2012)

Higher the level of consumer trust in the eco-labelling results in the higher the level of purchase of eco-friendly products was established in a study conducted on Danish organic label scheme to understand the factors involved in green product purchase among the Danish household by **Daugbjerg et al., (2014)**

Wasaya et al., (2021) examined green trust on energy savers consumers of different energy savers from south Punjab, Pakistan. A total of 306 consumers were involved in the study to learn about green trust, perceived quality of green products and perceived risk in buying Green products was found to be significant in purchase intention regarding green products. Environmental awareness moderates green purchase intention and its predictors considered for this study are green trust, green perceived quality, and green perceived risk.

Wang, et al., (2022) establishes the moderating effect of green trust. The data was collected from young graduates in Lahore, Pakistan. Snowball techniques are used to collect the data and 464 samples were collected. The study showed that green trust shows a moderating effect in between the green customer value and green brand positioning with green product purchase intention.

Green product purchase intention

Tang, Wang & Lu (2014) consumer attitude fully mediates the influence of consumer perceived effectiveness belief, and partly mediates the effect of environmental concern and functional value perception on consumer purchase intention toward low carbon emission vehicles.

Amin et al (2015) chose two stores where the movement of the consumers is high to collect the data. The questionnaire was designed to collect the data regarding product attitude, emotional benefits, functional attributes which gives information regarding green product positioning and also some questions about purchase intention of green [products. A total of 200 Malaysian consumers' responses were used for the study. The data analysis reveals that there is a strong positive influence of functional attributes and emotional benefit on product attitude while product attitude leaves a strong positive relationship on product purchase intention.

Chen, Chen & Tung (2018) intended to study the purchase intention of green products in Belt and Road countries. The data was collected from the appliance section in a departmental store where the consumers already purchased green products. The researchers were able to get 227 valid responses. The analysis of the data revealed that environmental attitude, social influence, monetary value and product attribute is found to be influencing purchase intention positively.

Wang, Zaman, & Alvi (2022) evaluates the mediating role of attitude toward the green brand and the moderating effect of green trust for the relationship of green brand positioning and green customer value with green purchase intention. Data was collected from the 464 University students with the help of snowball sampling technique. Results describe that green brand positioning and green customer value has noteworthy impact on green purchase intention. Results also illustrate that green brand positioning and green customer value has a significant impact on attitude toward green brands. Moreover, attitudes toward green brands

act as partial mediators for the relationship of green brand positioning and green customer value with green purchase intention. Furthermore, green trust act as moderator for the relationship of green brand positioning and green customer value with green purchase intention

Chen (2007) conducted a study In Taiwan, with the age group above twenty years The study identified that consumers' intention to purchase organic foods is determined by their attitude to organic foods purchase, subjective norm, perceived behavioural control, and perceived difficulty. Consumers' attitude to organic foods purchase is in turn positively determined by their attitude to organic foods,

A study conducted by **Ueasangkomsate (2016)** among Thailand respondents revealed that Consumers attitude regarding health aspect, local origin, environmental safety, and food safety has high correlation to purchase intention with respect to organic food

Michaelidou & Hassan (2010) finding highlights that consumers' ethical and environmental concerns and disposition to engage in ethical behaviours have an impact on their attitude and purchase intention towards organic and free-range produce

Green product positioning

Suki,(2016) has conducted a study in Malaysia among the customers having the experience of purchasing green products using a purposive sampling technique. A total 300 respondents were used in their study by a self-administered questionnaire. The study found that green brand positioning impact significantly on the green product purchase intention

Huang et al .,(2014) conducted a survey among Taiwan's Lifestyle and health sustainability club. 425 usable replies were collected from the respondents and the data was subjected to analysis. The result found that green brand knowledge and green brand positioning has a strong positive influence towards green attitude, green brand knowledge affects green brand attitude specifically, overall, green brand attitude plays a major role in green purchase intention.

Hartmann et al., (2005) there is a positive influence of green brand positioning on green brand attitude. Functional attributes and emotional benefits were the strategies used to test green brand positioning. 160 FINAL YEAR BUSINESS administration students from Spanish Basque country participated in the study.

Aulina & Yuliati (2017) conducted a study on a famous brand called the body shop which is well known for its green initiatives. Green brand positioning is having a positive influence towards green brand knowledge but not on attitude towards green brand. This green brand knowledge influences attitude towards green brands and at last attitude towards green brand influences green product purchase intention.

Pebrianti and Aulia (2021) stainless steel straw products pontianak city, Indonesia. Green brand knowledge and green brand positioning affects attitude towards green brands. Green brand positioning did not significantly affect purchase intention.

Situmorang et al., (2021) conducted a study to know about the moderating effect of attitude towards green brand on brand positioning and repurchase intention of green products. The

researchers opted for a purposive sampling method among environmentally friendly beauty cosmetic products consumers in Central java to collect the data for the study. The analysis of the result reveals that green brand positioning has a significant effect on purchase intention.

Green product promotion

Schuhwerk & Lefkoff-Hagius (1995) examined the purchase intention of the consumers upon the advertisement of a green laundry detergent. The purchase intention remains the same with people who are highly involved in environment and the attitude towards advertisement with green appeal and non-green appeal (in this case financial information of the product)/ But consumers who are less involved with environment possessed a greater purchase intention and is highly influenced by the advertisement related to green appeal/ the result shows that green advertisement is more persuasive among the people who are less involved with the environment. The research found that green advertisement creates a positive response towards the purchase intention of green products.

Teisel et al., (2002) have identified that eco-labelling dolphin safe labelling increased the market share of tuna. Affected consumer behaviour and increased the market share of the green product. Eco-labelling positively affects consumer and manufacturer behaviour

A study conducted by **Thøgersen, Haugaard & Olesen (2010)** emphasizes that Eco-labelling plays a major role in purchase of green products. Green product adoption depends upon the Motivation to adopt a sustainable product and the knowledge about the environmental issue and the trust gained by the organization which endorsed such ecolabelling to their product.

Grankvist et al., (2004) have pointed out that information about the environmental outcomes provided by Eco-labels did influence product preferences. Hence, Eco labelling can be an enabler. Also, how eco-labels might affect consumer opinions and attitudes towards green products and which enablers might increase its influence is also an area of study which should be explored, especially from an Indian context where such labels have just begun to show up. **Lee (2009)** has reported that peer influence was found to be the top predictor of green purchase

Green Product knowledge

Suki,(2016) . Found that when family members and friends have a deeper knowledge about green products motivates others to go for the purchase of green products

Situmorang et al.,(2021) conducted a study to know about the impact of green product knowledge on attitude towards green product and the effect of green brand knowledge on green purchase intention. The researchers opted purposive sampling method among environmental friendly beauty cosmetic products consumers in Central java to collect the data for the study. The received 175 usable google forms. Green brand knowledge has a positive effect on attitude towards green products but it is not having positive influence on repurchase intention of green products.

According to Aulina and Yuliati (2017), the desire of a customer to buy green brands to suit their needs is referred to as GPI. According to **Dahai et al. (2022) and Huang et al. (2014)**,

customers who have a positive opinion of green products may be more interested in green purchasing intentions.

Research Methodology

The research is to analyze the influence of green product positioning, green product knowledge, and attitude of customer amongst the people which would impact Product purchase Intention on green products and for the environment. Green Product Positioning is measured based on quality importance, environmental benefits. It consists of (6 items, Suki, N. M (2016)) Green Product knowledge of the sample population by taking the following criteria - opting as investment for long term, meeting their expectations, reasons for demand, environment friendliness. It consists (6 items, Suki, N. M (2016)). Attitude of customers is measured based on the green products reputation, reliability, its environmental performance and dependability, trustworthiness, meets expectation, keeps up promise and protects the environment. It consists (5 items, Suki, N. M (2016)). Product trust consists (5 items Chen, Y. S., & Chang, C. H. (2013)). Marketing mix consists (10 items, Sohail, M. S. (2017)). Product purchase intention consists (18 items Suki, N. M (2016), chan, R. Y. (2001) Sharaf, M. A., & Isa, F. M. (2017).

The questionnaire instruments were requested to be filled. Targeted sampling is used in the research to identify the people who used the green products at various purchase points of green products in Chennai region. 142 valid data were available for the analysis.

DATA ANALYSIS

The acquired data were validated using reliability test the cronbach's alpha value was Green product Positioning (.764), Green product Knowledge (.839), Attitude of Customer (.867), Product Trust (.889), Marketing mix (.885), Product Purchase Intention (.940), overall 0.916, which acknowledges that data are consistent with the research objective.

Pearson Correlation

H₁: To find the relationship between green product Positioning, Green product Knowledge, Attitude of customer, Marketing mix, Product trust, Product Purchase intention.

Table -1: Correlation

Correlation	Green Product Positioning	Green Product Knowledge	Attitude of Customer	Marketing Mix	Product Trust	Product Purchase Intention
Green Product Positioning	1	0.675**	.499**	.543**	.530**	0.547**
Green Product Knowledge	0.675**	1	.690**	.635**	.752**	.666**
Attitude of customer	.499**	.690**	1	.673**	.899**	.567**
Marketing Mix	.543**	.635**	.673**	1	.708**	0.673**
Product Trust	.530**	.752**	.899**	.708**	1	.611**
Product Purchase Intention	0.547**	.666**	.567**	0.673**	.611**	1

The Pearson correlation table proves that there is a significant relationship between the variable green product positioning, green product knowledge, green product attitude, market mix, product trust and product purchase intention. The R value or relationship strength between green product positioning and green product knowledge, green product attitude, Marketing mix, Product trust, Purchase intention is **0.675, 0.499, 0.543, 0.530, 0.547** and relationship strength between green product knowledge and green product attitude, Marketing mix, Product trust, purchase intention is **0.690, 0.635, 0.752, 0.666**. The relationship strength R value between green product attitude and Marketing mix, Product trust, Purchase Intention is **0.673, 0.899, 0.567**. The relationship strength R value between Marketing Mix, Product trust and purchase intention is **0.708, 0.673**. The relationship strength R value between Product Trust and Purchase Intention is **0.611**.

Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple regression analysis was used to test the research hypotheses and to explore the strength of a relationship among variables. Coefficients found that green brand knowledge and Product trust have significant and positive relationship with green products purchase intention at p-value less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$). However, there is no positive and significant relationship between attitude of customer, green product positioning the p-value is 0.278, attitude of customer the P-value .902 and Marketing mix the p-value is .710 towards green products purchase intention because which is greater than 0.05.

H₂: Product purchase intention does not depend on Green Product Positioning, Green Product Knowledge, Attitude of Customer, Product Trust, and Marketing Mix

Table- 2: Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adj R ²	Std. Er of the Estimate
1	.744 ^a	.554	.533	.43153

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Green Product Positioning, Green Product Knowledge, Attitude of Customer, Product Trust, Marketing Mix

Table-3: Anova^a

Model	Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	24.775	5	4.955	26.609	.000 ^b
Residual	19.925	107	.186		
Total	44.700	112			

Among the green brand positioning and green brand knowledge, product trust has highest beta value (0.428) the value shows product trust is the strongest predictor for purchase intention, followed by green product knowledge, green brand positioning, marketing mix, attitude towards customer with beta value of 0.329, 0.113, 0.054, -.017.

Table- 4: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Er	Beta			Lower Bond	Upper Bond
Constant	.412	.360		1.145	.255	-.301	1.126
GPP	.113	.104	.098	1.090	.278	-.093	.320
GPK	.329	.116	.322	2.848	.005	.100	.558
ATC	-.017	.136	-.018	-.124	.902	-.287	.253
PT	.428	.107	.384	3.993	.000	.215	.640
MM	.054	.145	.062	.373	.710	-.234	.342

(GPP) Green Product Positioning, (GPK) Green Product Knowledge, (ATC) Attitude of Customer, (PT) Product Trust, (MM) Marketing Mix

DISCUSSION

Green purchase product intention is influenced by green product trust and green product knowledge in this study. Green product trust could be improved when the product kept up the promises that were made towards environmental protection (Also consumers would be willing to purchase the product based on the trust that the product created (**Krystallis & Chryssohoidis, 2005**). The trust would be developed when the product meets the expectations of the consumers with regard to environmental performance. Authorised government or other respective bodies could provide trustworthy labels to the product that truly meet the environmental functionality (**Darnall, Ponting, & Vazquez-Brust, 2012**).

Green product knowledge plays a major role in the purchase intention of green products. **Chen, K., & Deng, T. (2016)**. A strong knowledge regarding the product and its tangible or intangible benefits that it would create to the environment in a long run is fundamental knowledge that the purchasers should know would give inclination towards the purchase of green products to a greater extent (**suki, 2016**). When the consumer accumulated more knowledge about green products and its availability eventually increases the purchase intention (**Zhuang et al., 2021**)

Implications of the study

The study implies that creating trust about their product should be a prime focus of the green product manufacturers/ sellers. Trust worthiness of a product would create a brand image for the product as well as the factor to be practiced in all walks of the product by their manufacturers / sellers. Imparting knowledge about the green product could be planned.

References:

1. Chen, K., & Deng, T. (2016). Research on the green purchase intentions from the perspective of product knowledge. *Sustainability*, 8(9), 943.
2. Zhuang, W., Luo, X., & Riaz, M. U. (2021). On the factors influencing green purchase intention: A meta-analysis approach. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 644020.

3. Chen, Y. S., & Chang, C. H. (2013). The influences of green perceived quality, green perceived risk, and green satisfaction. *Management Decision*, 51(1), 63-82.
4. Suki, N. M. (2016). Green product purchase intention: impact of green brands, attitude, and knowledge. *British Food Journal*.
5. Darnall, N., Ponting, C., & Vazquez-Brust, D. A. (2012). Why consumers buy green. In *Green growth: Managing the transition to a sustainable economy* (pp. 287-308). Springer, Dordrecht.
6. Krystallis, A., & Chrysosoidis, G. (2005). Consumers' willingness to pay for organic food: Factors that affect it and variation per organic product type. *British food journal*.
7. Tung, S. J., Shih, C. C., Wei, S., & Chen, Y. H. (2012). Attitudinal inconsistency toward organic food in relation to purchasing intention and behavior: An illustration of Taiwan consumers. *British Food Journal*, 114(7), 997-1015.
8. Daugbjerg, C., Smed, S., Andersen, L. M., & Schwartzman, Y. (2014). Improving eco-labelling as an environmental policy instrument: Knowledge, trust and organic consumption. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, 16(4), 559-575.
9. Wasaya, A., Saleem, M. A., Ahmad, J., Nazam, M., Khan, M., & Ishfaq, M. (2021). Impact of green trust and green perceived quality on green purchase intentions: a moderation study. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 23(9), 13418-13435.
10. Wang, Y. M., Zaman, H. M. F., & Alvi, A. K. (2022). Linkage of green brand positioning and green customer value with green purchase intention: the mediating and moderating role of attitude toward green brand and green trust. *Sage Open*, 12(2), 21582440221102441.
11. Tang, Y., Wang, X., & Lu, P. (2014). Chinese consumer attitude and purchase intent towards green products. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Business Administration*.
12. Amin, M., Uthamaputhran, S., & Ali, F. (2015). The effectiveness of green product positioning and marketing strategies towards purchase intention in Malaysia. *International Journal of Innovation and Learning*, 17(4), 516-528.
13. Chen, C. C., Chen, C. W., & Tung, Y. C. (2018). Exploring the consumer behavior of intention to purchase green products in belt and road countries: An empirical analysis. *Sustainability*, 10(3), 854.
14. Wang, Y. M., Zaman, H. M. F., & Alvi, A. K. (2022). Linkage of green brand positioning and green customer value with green purchase intention: the mediating and moderating role of attitude toward green brand and green trust. *Sage Open*, 12(2), 21582440221102441.
15. Chen, M. F. (2007). Consumer attitudes and purchase intentions in relation to organic foods in Taiwan: Moderating effects of food-related personality traits. *Food Quality and preference*, 18(7), 1008-1021.
16. Ueasangkomsate, P., & Santiteerakul, S. (2016). A study of consumers' attitudes and intention to buy organic foods for sustainability. *Procedia Environmental Sciences*, 34, 423-430.
17. Michaelidou, N., & Hassan, L. M. (2010). Modeling the factors affecting rural consumers' purchase of organic and free-range produce: A case study of consumers from the Island of Arran in Scotland, UK. *Food Policy*, 35(2), 130-139.
18. Huang, Yi-Chun; Yang, Minli; Wang, Yu-Chun (2014). Effects of green brand on green purchase intention. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 32(3), 250-268. doi:10.1108/MIP-10-2012-0105
19. Hartmann, P., Ibáñez, V. A., & Sainz, F. J. F. (2005). Green branding effects on attitude: functional versus emotional positioning strategies. *Marketing intelligence & planning*.

20. Aulina, L., & Yuliati, E. (2017, November). The effects of green brand positioning, green brand knowledge, and attitude towards green brand on green products purchase intention. In International Conference on Business and Management Research (ICBMR 2017) (pp. 548-557). Atlantis Press.
21. Pebrianti, W., & Aulia, M. (2021). The Effect of Green Brand Knowledge and Green Brand Positioning on Purchase Intention Mediated by Attitude Towards Green Brand: Study on Stainless Steel Straw Products by Zero Waste. *JDM (Jurnal Dinamika Manajemen)*, 12(2).
22. SITUMORANG, T. P., INDRIANI, F., SIMATUPANG, R. A., & SOESANTO, H. (2021). Brand positioning and repurchase intention: The effect of attitude toward green brands. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(4), 491-499.
23. Schuhwerk, M. E., & Lefkoff-Hagius, R. (1995). Green or non-green? Does type of appeal matter when advertising a green product?. *Journal of advertising*, 24(2), 45-54
24. Teisl, M. F., Roe, B., & Hicks, R. L. (2002). Can eco-labels tune a market? Evidence from dolphin-safe labeling. *Journal of environmental Economics and Management*, 43(3), 339-359.
25. Thøgersen, J. (2002). Promoting green consumer behavior with eco-labels. *New Tools for Environmental Protection*, 83-104.
26. Thøgersen, J., Haugaard, P., & Olesen, A. (2010). Consumer responses to ecolabels. *European journal of marketing*.
27. Darnall, N., Ponting, C., & Vazquez-Brust, D. A. (2012). Why consumers buy green. In *Green growth: Managing the transition to a sustainable economy* (pp. 287-308). Springer, Dordrecht.
28. Zhuang, W., Luo, X., & Riaz, M. U. (2021). On the factors influencing green purchase intention: A meta-analysis approach. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 644020.
29. Chan, R. Y. (2001). Determinants of Chinese consumers' green purchase behavior. *Psychology & marketing*, 18(4), 389-413.
30. Sharaf, M. A., & Isa, F. M. (2017). Factors influencing students' intention to purchase green products: A case study in Universiti Utara Malaysia. *Pertanika Journal of Social Science and Humanities*, 25(2), 240-245.
31. Sohail, M. S. (2017). Green marketing strategies: how do they influence consumer-based brand equity?. *Journal for Global Business Advancement*, 10(3), 229-243
32. Chen, Y. S., & Chang, C. H. (2013). Towards green trust: The influences of green perceived quality, green perceived risk, and green satisfaction. *Management Decision*.